

Original Article

Isolation of Pathogenic Bacteria from Inanimate Surfaces and contaminated Equipments in Intensive Care Unit at Zawia Teaching Hospital, Libya

Salma Alamari *

Department of Anesthesia and Intensive care, Faculty of Medical Technology, Zawia University, Zawia, Libya.

ARTICLE INFO

DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.4127274](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4127274)

* **Salma Alamari:** Department of Anaesthesia and Intensive care, Faculty of Medical Technology, Zawia University, Zawia, Libya, libyalibya1977@yahoo.com

Received: 22-09-2020

Accepted: 12-10-2020

Keywords: Hospital, acquired infection, Nosocomial infections, ICU.

This work is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution International License (CC BY 4.0).

ABSTRACT

Bacterial infections are responsible for great number of mortalities in the Intensive Care Units (ICUs). ICU-acquired infections are a challenging health problem worldwide, especially when caused by multidrug-resistant (MDR) pathogens. Cross-transmission of microorganisms from inanimate surfaces may have a significant role in ICU-acquired colonization and infections. This study aimed at isolating and identifying the pathogenic bacteria from equipment surface in the intensive care unit at Zawia teaching hospital, and to evaluate the impact of sterilization and disinfectants on the equipment used in these ICUs. **METHODS:** The study was carried in the period from April to May 2018. A total of 56 frequently used equipments and devices in ICUs were sampled by using a sterile swab moistened with Trypticase Soy Broth (TSB) medium, according to standard bacteriological procedures. Data were presented as counts and percentage using Excel spread data sheath. **RESULTS:** Out of 56 samples, 7(12.5%) shows no bacterial growth, 23(41.1%) samples exhibited the presence of pathogenic bacteria (*Escherichia coli*, *Serratia marcescens*, *Staphylococcus hemolytic*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Acinetobacter baumannii*, *Klebsiella pneumonia*, Coagulase negative *Staphylococci*, *Serratia marcescens*), and 26(46.4%) samples contaminated with non-pathogenic *Diphtheria* and coagulase-negative *staphylococci* and mixed flora. **CONCLUSION:** There were no sterilization and disinfection in ICU at Zawia Teaching hospital, and the pathogenic bacteria everywhere.

Cite this article: Alamari S and Algeblaue G. Isolation of Pathogenic Bacteria from Inanimate Surfaces and contaminated Equipments in Intensive Care Unit at Zawia Teaching Hospital, Libya. *Alq J Med App Sci.* 2020;3(2):82-88.

INTRODUCTION

Hospital-acquired infection (HAI) also called a nosocomial infection is an infection which is generally supported by the environmental condition of the hospital, such as an infection that is acquired by a patient during its hospital visit or one which is developing from amongst the hospital staff [1]. Intensive care unit (ICU)-acquired infections are a

major cause of morbidity and mortality worldwide [2].

The contamination may occur either by transfer of microorganisms contaminating health-workers' hands or direct patient shedding of microorganisms in the immediate environment of a patient's bed [3], contamination of equipment by bacteria is common, turning them into reservoirs of these microorganisms,

enabling the colonization and cross infection of patients, complicating prognosis and favoring HAI outbreaks, mostly by microorganisms multiresistant to antibiotics commonly applied in therapeutics [4], which implies severe limitations to the treatment of hospital infections, posing a great threat to public health [5].

It has been reported that HAI caused by both gram-positive and gram-negative bacteria are able to survive up to months on dry inanimate surfaces, with longer persistence under humid and lower-temperature conditions [6]. Different organisms are related to contaminations in hospital environments and HAI processes [7], but the main pathogens include oxacillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (ORSA), vancomycin-resistant *Enterococcus* sp (VRE), and more recently, extended-spectrum beta-lactamases (ESBL) and carbapenem-resistant *Acinetobacter baumannii* [8,9]. Factors that may affect the transfer of microorganisms from one surface to another and cross-contamination rates are type of organisms, source and destination surfaces, humidity level, and size of inoculums [10,11]. Other factors playing a role in contamination and cross-transmission rate in the ICU may include hand hygiene compliance, nurse-staffing levels, frequency/number of colonized or infected patients, ICU structural features (e.g., single-bed or multi-bed ICU rooms) and adoption of antibiotic stewardship programs [12-14].

A study conducted in Brazil revealed that the percentage of ICU equipment contamination was 94.4%, and the most frequently isolated microorganisms were *acinetobacter* sp., *staphylococcus aureus* and *pseudomonas* spp. About 75% of *acinetobacter* sp. was resistant to piperacillin associated to tazobactam, meropenem and levofloxacin. Similarly, 36.3% of *S. aureus* showed resistance to oxacillin and 10% of *Pseudomonas* sp. was resistant to the drugs tested [15].

Another study performed in reported that the most common pathogens isolated from Device-Associated Healthcare-Associated Infections (DA-HAI) patients were *Klebsiella pneumoniae* (24.6%), *Escherichia coli* (21.9%), and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (20.2%) [16].

A local study conducted in El-khomes hospital of Libya revealed that *Staphylococcus* spp. (76.4%) and *Bacillus cereus* (27.3%) were the most commonly isolated organisms from healthcare workers and environment surfaces in ICU and operation theatre [17].

Therefore, the main aim of the study was to isolate and identify the most common pathogenic bacteria found in ICU surfaces of Zawia Teaching Hospital, and to provide an evidence of inanimate surfaces and equipment contamination, as well as to find out which bacteria may cause the nosocomial infection.

METHODS

Study settings

This study was carried out in the period from April to May 2018, by sampling equipments and machines inside the ICUs of Zawia Teaching Hospital. The visited ICUs were three ICUs equipped with twenty beds per ICU. Each bed connected with monitor, mechanical ventilation (MV), and control panel. Samples were collected from different sites including; keyboard, screen, and the arm of the MV; the screen, and power control of the monitor; patient's bed from the right position; control panel. These sites were frequented touch by doctors and other staff workers in the ICUs.

Sample techniques

Samples were collected randomly in different days by assembling seven samples from different locations in the same bed. A total of 56 sample were collected using a sterile swab which moistened with Trypticase Soy Broth (TSB) medium to allows for microbial

growth. After that the swab were spun around their axis over the previously selected surfaces they were again stored in the medium and immediately transported to Alfa private Laboratory in Zawia city. Inside the laboratory, the samples were incubated for 48 hours at 37°C to allow microbial growth. After that, samples were cultured in blood agar, McConkey agar, and salt mantiol agar, and incubated for 24 hours at 37°C.

Suspected bacteria were growing to form colonies used the standard bacteriological procedures, in order to identify the bacterial phenotypical, and recorded the shape features of the colonies and the gram staining was done to identifying the genera and species of the bacteria isolated by microscopic examination. For culturing the Enterobacteriaceae family, the carbohydrate fermentation test was used in Triple Sugar Iron (TSI), the biochemical tests (Sulfide Indole Motility (SIM), Simmons' citrate and Christensen's Urea Agar growth mediums).

To identify the glucose-non fermenting gram-negative bacteria, oxidase and polymyxin B tests were used. The identification of Staphylococcus spp was done by catalase, DNase and Novobiocin tests. Streptococcus spp were identified through the characteristics of hemolytic activity on the blood agar, the use of Bile esculin agar, Brain Heart infusion (BHI) + NaCl 6.5% and optochin tests. All the biochemical tests were used to identified and isolated bacteria was carried by Alfa Laboratory staff.

Data analysis

Descriptive statistics were used to present the results in the form of counts and percentages, using Microsoft excel data sheath.

RESULTS

The results of the current study reported that, out of 56 samples taken from ICU types of equipment and machines, 7(12.5%) shows no bacterial growth, 23(41.1%) samples exhibited the presence of pathogenic bacteria (Escherichia coli, Serratia marcescens, Staphylococcus hemolytic, Pseudomonas aeruginosa, Acinetobacter baumannii, Klebsiella pneumonia, Coagulase negative Staphylococci, Serratia marcescens), and 26(46.4%) samples contaminated with non-pathogenic Diphtheria and coagulase-negative staphylococci and mixed flora. Table 1 represents the types and percentages of ICU equipments contaminated with pathogenic and non-pathogenic bacteria were as the followings; Escherichia coli 7.1%, S marcescens 6.2 %, P. aeruginosa 6.1%, A. baumannii 4.6%, K pneumonia 6.2%, S. hemolytic 3.1%, CoNS 3%.

Table 1. Types and percentages of bacteria isolated from the visited ICUs

Type of bacteria	Number	Percentage
<i>E coli</i> + NPD	4	7.1 %
<i>S marcescens</i>	2	3.1 %
<i>S hemolyticus</i>	2	3.1 %
<i>P aeruginosa</i> + NPD	3	4.6 %
<i>A baumannii</i>	3	4.6 %
<i>K pneumonia</i> + NPD	2	3.1 %
CoNS + NPD	1	1.5 %
CoNS	1	1.5 %
<i>S marcescens</i> + NPD	2	3.1 %
<i>K pneumonia</i>	2	3.1 %
<i>P aeruginosa</i>	1	1.5 %
NPD	26	40 %
No growth	7	10.8 %
Total	56	100%

NPD. Nonpathogenic Diphtheria; CoNS. Coagulase-Negative Staphylococci

Figure 1 displays the number of pathogenic and non-pathogenic bacteria reached approximately 87.5 %. This confirms the presence of bacterial

contamination in ICUs, which may lead to HAI as well as nosocomial infection.

Figure1. The percentage of bacterial types compared with a total number of bacteria.

As shown in table 2, the most common contaminated sites with pathogenic bacteria were the mechanical ventilation surfaces (screen and keyboard were more contaminated than the arm of MV), followed by patient’s bed sites especially from the both bed arms. The most common type of bacteria found in different sites in the ICU were represented in figure 2.

Table 2. ICU Equipments contaminated with bacteria

Equipments and Surfaces	Type of Contaminated Bacteria
Keyboard of mechanical ventilation	<i>K pneumonia</i> , NPD, <i>E coli</i> + NPD, CoNS+ NPD
Screen of mechanical ventilation	NPD, Mix flora / CoNS, <i>K pneumonia</i> , <i>P aeruginosa</i> + NPD, <i>S marcescens</i>
Arm of mechanical ventilation	NPD
Screen of heart monitor	CoNS
Turn on/off of heart monitor	NPD, <i>A baumannii</i>
Patient’s bed	NPD, <i>P aeruginosa</i> , <i>Shemolyticus</i>
A plate of control touching in bed	NPD

DISCUSSION

This study aimed at identifying the most common pathogenic bacteria contaminates the equipment surface of ICUs at Zawia teaching hospital, and to evaluate the impact of sterilization and disinfectants that had applied on the surfaces of equipments in ICU. Sterilization and disinfection are essential for preventing the transport of infectious pathogens to patients. The results of the current study confirmed the inappropriateness of sterilization and disinfection program of these ICUs, as the pathogenic bacteria were presented on the equipments surface, which may cause the occurrence of HAI.

Earlier studies had documented the lack of compliance with the established guidelines for disinfection and sterilization [18], which was responsible on the prevalence of HAI in some developing countries ranging from 17.9% in Tunisia

[19], 7.8% in Morocco [20], and 14.8% in Tanzania [21]. This high incidence rate can be explaining the deficiency of infection control programs in different countries. The findings of the current study reported 41.1% contamination rate of pathogenic. The highest number of isolated bacteria from equipment surface were NPD or diphtheroid isolated in pure culture and mixed with other pathogenic bacteria.

Diphtheroid is known as aerobic, non-sporulating, pleomorphic gram-positive bacilli which are more uniformly stained, lack the metachromatic granules and are arranged in a palisade manner. Although it usually commensals the skin and mucous membranes, it frequently reported in association with nosocomial infections and a vast majority of these infections are exhibiting antibiotic resistance [22]. Diphtheroid able to form a biofilm on the medical equipment, which is difficult to treat and may cause chronic infection, for catheter and prostatic infections causing recurrent infections thereby to biofilm resistant to antibiotics [23]. This biofilm matrix causing antibiotic resistance, and responsible to delayed penetration of antibiotic into the microorganisms in the biofilm, as a cause of alteration of their physiological mechanism and growth rate due to the biofilm manner of growth [24]. Diphtheroid were isolated in different sites in this study, and were co-existed with pathogenic bacteria (G-ve) and (G+ve). This environment enhances the biofilm formation and lead to antibiotic resistance. The current results also displayed that mechanical ventilation surfaces were contaminated with mixed bacteria e.g. NAD.

Inanimate surfaces considered as the source of hospital acquired infections with numerous gram-negative species, such as *Acinetobacter* spp., *E coli*, *Klebsiella* spp., *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Serratia marcescens*, or *Shigella* spp., that can also survive for months on these surfaces [6]. *Staphylococcus aureus* is a major cause of infection in both healthcare and community settings, and it considered as one of the

most common causes of HAI reported to the National Nosocomial Infections Surveillance (NNIS) system, including surgical site infection and ventilator-associated pneumonia [25]. In this study, the species of staphylococci were CoNS with mixed flora and S hemolytic. Previous local study in Elkhomes hospital also reported that the contamination rate was 76.4 % *S. aureus* that isolated from the anterior nares of healthcare workers and one of them was MRSA [17]. *A. baumannii* was 4.6 % from isolated bacteria in our study. The genus *Acinetobacter* have diversity levels of nutrition and metabolic this allows *Acinetobacter* genus to obtain variety of substrates as carbon sources. It is active on the surfaces for days or weeks in hospital environments [8]. The existence of genus *Acinetobacter* in various ICU may causes clinical complications [26] and leads to acquired resistance to carbapenem antibiotics [27]. Further studies are warrant to estimate the prevalence of this bacterium on hospital equipment as and to determine the behavior of these strains in this kind of environment [8].

CONCLUSION

The findings of this study reported different types pathogenic bacteria from an inanimate surface of ICUs were present, that suggest the failure of sterilization and disinfection in these ICUs. Bacterial contamination may contribute to ICU-acquired colonization or infection; therefore, the further studies are needed to evaluate this correlation of the antibiotic-resistance bacteria, nonpathogenic diphtheria, and many others.

Disclaimer

The article has not been previously presented or published, and is not part of a thesis project.

Conflict of Interest

There are no financial, personal, or professional conflicts of interest to declare.

REFERENCE

- [1] Grace E. T., and Robert P. G. (1993). An Overview of Nosocomial Infections, Including the Role of the Microbiology Laboratory, *J. Clinical microbiology reviews*, 6(4): 428-442.
- [2] Vincent J. L., Rello J., Marshall J., Silva E., Anzueto A., and Martin C. D. (2009). International study of the prevalence and outcomes of infection in intensive care units, *J. JAMA*;302(21):2323-9.
- [3] Hayden M. K., Blom D.W., Lyle E. A., Moore C.G., and Weinstein R.A. (2008). Risk of hand or glove contamination after contact with patients colonized with vancomycin-resistant enterococcus or the colonized patients' environment. *InfectControl*;29(02):149- 54.
- [4] Polin R. A., Denson S., Brady M.T. (2012). Committee on Fetus and Newborn; Committee on Infectious Diseases. Strategies for prevention of health care-associated infections in the NICU, *J. Pediatrics*;192(4): e1085-93.
- [5] Dettori M., Piana A., Deriu M. G., Curto P. L., Cossu A., and Musumeci R. (2014). Outbreak of multidrug-resistant *Acinetobacter baumannii* in an intensive care unit, *J. New Microbiol*; 37(2):185-91.
- [6] Kramer A., Schwebke I., Kampf G. (2006). How long do nosocomial pathogens persist on inanimate surfaces? A systematic review, *J. BMC Infect Dis*;6(1): 130.
- [7] Juayang A. C., Reyes G. B., Rama A. J.G., and Gallega C. T. (2014). Antibiotic resistance profiling of *Staphylococcus aureus* isolated from clinical specimens in a tertiary hospital from 2010 to 2012, *J. Interdiscip Perspect Infect Dis*; 898457.
- [8] Cieslinski J. M., Arend L., Tuon F.F., Silva E. P., Ekermann R. G., and Dalla-Costa L.M. (2013). Molecular epidemiology characterization of OXA-23 carbapenemase-producing *Acinetobacter baumannii* isolated from 8 Brazilian hospitals using repetitive sequence-based PCR, *J. Diagn Microbiol Infect Dis*; 77(4):337-40.
- [9] Jeon J. H., Hong M. K., Lee J. H., Lee J.J., Park K. S., and Karim A. M. (2014). Structure of ADC-68, a novel carbapenem-hydrolyzing class C extended spectrum β -lactamase isolated from *Acinetobacter baumannii*, *J. Acta Cryst*; D70:2924-36
- [10] Dancer S. J. (2008). Importance of the environment in meticillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* acquisition: the case for hospital cleaning, *J. Lancet Infect Dis*;8(2):101-13.
- [11] Pittet D., Allegranzi B., Sax H., Dharan S., Pessoa-Silva C.L., and Donaldson L. (2006). Evidence-based model for hand transmission during patient care and the role of improved practices, *J. Lancet Infect Dis*;6(10):641-52.
- [12] Montero J.G., Lerma F. Á., Gallego P. R., Martínez M. P., Rocha L. Á., and Gaite F.B. (2015). Combating resistance in intensive care: the multimodal approach of the Spanish ICU "Zero Resistance" program, *J. Crit Care*;19(1):114.
- [13] Rohr U., Kaminski A., Wilhelm M., Jurzik L., Gatermann S., and Muhr G. (2009). Colonization of patients and contamination of the patients' environment by MRSA under conditions of single-room isolation, *J. Hyg Environ Health*;212(2):209-15.
- [14] Shokoohi H. A., Armstrong P., Tansek R. (2015). Emergency department ultrasound probe infection control: Challenges and solutions, *J. Open Access Emerg Med*;7:1-9.
- [15] Igor V. R., Patrick M. F., Thaísa G. F., Sibeles R. O. (2015). Resistance of bacteria isolated from equipment in an intensive care unit, *J. Acta Paul Enferm*; 28(5):433-9.
- [16] Inam D. K., Atoshi B., Sheshadri K., Shaleen T., Priyanka P., Anupam C. (2017). Device-Associated Healthcare-Associated Infections (DA-HAI) and the caveat of multiresistance in a multidisciplinary intensive care unit, *J. Med J Armed Forces India* ;73(3):222-231
- [17] Ali M. M., Aburowes A. H., Albakush A. M., Rzeg M. M., and Alrtail A. (2014). Identification of multidrug-resistant bacteria and *Bacillus cereus* from healthcare workers and environmental surfaces in a hospital, *J. Libyan J Med* ;(9):25794.
- [18] Uttley A. H., Simpson R. A. (1994). Audit of bronchoscope disinfection: a survey of procedures in England and Wales and incidents of mycobacterial contamination, *J. Hosp. Infect.* 1994; 26:301-8.
- [19] Kallel H., Bahoul M., Ksibi H., Damma k. H., Chelly H., and Hamida C.B. (2005). Prevalence of hospital-

- acquired infection in a Tunisian hospital, *J. Hosp Infect* 2005; 59:343-7.
- [20] Jroundi I., Khoudri I., Azzouzi A., and Zeggwagh A.A. (2007). Prevalence of hospital acquired infection in a Moroccan university hospital, *J. Am J Infect Control*;35(6):412.
- [21] Goslin R., Mbatia R., Savage A., Mulligan J. A., and Reyburn H. (2003). Prevalence of hospital- acquired infections in a tertiary referral hospital in northern Tanzania, *J. Ann Trop Med Parasitol* ;97:69-73.
- [22] Purbasha G., Khushboo K. M., Yugal K. S., and Rabindra N. M. (2012). Co-infection of Herpes genitalis with *Corynebacterium amycolatum*: A rare case report from the district of Western Maharashtra, India, *J. JCDR*;6(7):1298-300
- [23] De P. G., Montini L., Pennisi M.A., Bernini V., Maviglia R., and Bello G. (2014). High dose Tigecycline in critically ill patients with severe infections due to multidrug resistant bacteria, *J. Crit Care*;18(3):R90.
- [24] Donlan R.M., Costerton J.W. (2002) Biofilms: survival mechanisms of clinically Relevant microorganisms, *J. Clin Microbiol Rev*;15(2):167-93.
- [25] National Nosocomial Infections Surveillance (NNIS) system report, data summary from January 1992– June 2001. (2001). *J. Am J Infect Control*; 29:404-21
- [26] Allegranzi B., Nejad S. B., Combescure C., Graafmans W., Attar H., and Donaldson L. (2011). Burden of endemic health-care-associated infection in developing countries: systematic review and meta-analysis, *J. Lancet*; 337(9761):228-41.
- [27] Dettori M., Piana A., Deriu M.G., Curto P.L., Cossu A and Musumeci R. (2014). Outbreak of multidrug-resistant *Acinetobacter baumannii* in an intensive care unit, *J. New Microbiol*; 37(2):185-91.